

Studies on complexes of cobalt-, nickel-, copper-, zinc- and cadmium(II) with Schiff base derived from 3-aminodibenzofuran and salicylaldehyde

A. Kriza^a, A. Reiss^{b*}, S. Florea^b and T. Câproiu^c

^aFaculty of Chemistry, University of Bucharest, Dimbrava Rosie, 23, Romania

^bFaculty of Sciences, University of Craiova, A. I. Cuza, 13, Craiova, Romania

^cCentre of Organic Chemistry, Splaiul Independentei, 202B, Bucharest, Romania

Manuscript received 16 April 1999, revised 25 October 1999, accepted 26 November 1999

3-Aminodibenzofuran reacts with salicylaldehyde in the presence of a metal ion giving crystalline complexes of the type [ML(OAc).H₂O], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} and L = monoanion of the Schiff base. The complexes are found to have four coordination number.

The chemistry of metal complexes with Schiff base ligands prepared by using a variety of carbonylic compounds and aromatic amines, has been extensively studied¹.

The synthesis of metal complexes with Schiff base derived from 3-aminodibenzofuran with various aldehydes was made in two ways : (i) the synthesis of complexes by template reaction and (ii) first, the synthesis of Schiff base and then synthesis of metal complexes. Here, we report the synthesis by template reaction and characterisation of five complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with the Schiff base (HL)²,

Results and Discussion

The complexes obtained are microcrystalline coloured powders, whose melting points are higher than that of the free ligand. They are stable at room temperature and their solubility in common inorganic and organic solvents is medium. The molecular formula of complexes is [ML(OAc).H₂O], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} and L = the monoanion of the Schiff base. The molar electronic conductivities (10–15 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMF solutions at room temperature¹³) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes.

The Schiff base shows a broad IR band at 3400 cm⁻¹ which is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding involving hydrogen of the phenolic group and nitrogen atom of amine group⁴. This band disappears in complexes indicating the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by metal ion. The ν_{C=N} band appears at 1600–1603 cm⁻¹ in the metal

complexes as compared to that at 1609 cm⁻¹ in Schiff base. This decrease (6–9 cm⁻¹) indicates the coordination of nitrogen of azomethine group with the metal ion. The strong ligand band at 1280 cm⁻¹ appears at 1303 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, thus showing a shift towards higher regions by 23 cm⁻¹. This band is characteristic of ν_{C-O} and its shift further supports the formation of the M–O bond^{5,6}. The metal complexes also show some new bands at 580–560 and 460–420 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N}, respectively^{7,8}. In the spectra of all the metal complexes, the presence of coordinated water is shown by the appearance of bands at 3300–3350 cm⁻¹ followed by another additional band at 840–860 cm⁻¹, respectively^{8,9}.

The Schiff base shows ¹H NMR signal at δ 9.74 (s, -N=CH-) and ¹³C NMR peak at δ 162.7. The evidence for the bonding mode of the ligand is provided by the ¹H NMR spectrum of the diamagnetic nickel(II) complex. The positions of the ligand signals due to H-2 and H-4 protons (in *para*-position of the nitrogen atom) from the dibenzofuranic moiety at δ 7.30 and 7.48 shift towards lower field in the complex at δ 7.32 and 7.50, respectively, because of the coordination of nitrogen atom (the spectra were recorded in the same solvent CDCl₃). The chemical shifts are weak probably due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the Schiff base. The signal assigned to the azomethine proton exhibits a similar shift but the signal of the carbon atom from the azomethine group is not shifted on complexation. The signal of the phenolic proton in the free ligand at δ 12.7 ppm (intramolecularly H-bonded phenolic group) is absent in the spectrum of the complex, thus confirming the deprotonation of the phenolic group on complex formation.

The magnetic moment value for the Co^{II} complex (4.54 B.M.) indicates tetrahedral stereochemistry¹⁰. The electronic spectrum shows two bands at 7200 and 16200 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ⁴A₂(F) → ⁴T₁(F) and ⁴A₂(F) → ⁴T₁(P) transitions, respectively. The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic. The electronic spectrum exhibits four bands at 18700, 20800, 26700 and 32500 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g and π → π*(L). These results suggest a square-planar configuration for the Ni^{II} complex¹¹.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of the Cu^{II} complex (1.86 B.M.) indicates the presence of one free electron. The electronic spectrum exhibits three bands at 14700, 20600 and 26600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ³B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and charge transfer, respectively. These observations suggest square-planar structure for the Cu^{II} complex¹². The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and they show two peaks in UV domain due to ligand transitions only.

The compound [CuL(OAc).H₂O] presents a very intensive EPR spectrum with anisotropic parameters : g_{||} = 2.2402 and g_⊥ = 2.0702. As g_{||} > g_⊥, the line shape suggests a tetragonal geometry specific for Cu^{II} in a square-planar coordination¹³. Such a geometry is also corroborated by electronic spectrum of the compound.

On the basis of the above evidences, a structure in which metal ions have four coordination number, may be proposed.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. 3-Aminodibenzofuran and the Schiff base were prepared according to literature method^{14,2}.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on an Unicam UV2-300 spectrophotometer. EPR spectrum was registered in powder form at room temperature using an

Art-5-Ifin Bucharest spectrometer, operated in X band, the modulation of magnetic field being 100 kHz and Mn²⁺ used as internal standard. Both ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian-Gemini 300 BB instrument. The molar conductivity was determined by using OK-102 (Hungary) conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature.

The complexes were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of 3-aminodibenzofuran, metal acetate and salicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing the solution for 2 h at 100°. The resulting metal complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

References

1. W. L. Kwik and Alice W. N. Tay, *Polyhedron*, 1990, 9, 1293; L. Henning, R. Kirmse, O. Hammerich, S. Larsen, H. Frydendahl, H. Toftlund and J. Becher, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1995, 234, 67; A. M. A. Hassaan, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1997, 106, 73.
2. V. Fărcăsan, I. Cristea and S. Florea, *Stud. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai, Chimia*, 1977, 2, 13.
3. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
4. L. J. Bellamy, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1954.
5. H. E. L. Khadem, *Z. Anorg. Alleg. Chem.*, 1963, 72, 325.
6. R. N. Prasad and J. P. Tandon, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 35, 1173.
7. B. Hutchinson, D. Eversdyk and S. Olbricht, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A*, 1974, 30, 1605.
8. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
9. I. Gama, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1961, 34, 760.
10. D. H. Busch in "Cobalt", ed. R. S. Young, American Chemical Society, 1970.
11. H. B. Gray and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 260.
12. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectra", Elsevier, New York, 1984.
13. B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 143.
14. V. Fărcăsan, S. Florea and R. Beju, *Stud. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai, Chimia*, 1970, 1, 63.